

Perception of HND Students towards the Use of Virtual Learning Systems in Federal Polytechnic Ede, Osun State

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Abstract

The need to maximise the rate of use of technological devices for educational purpose in order to boost the acceptance rate, acquaintance, and competency in the use of virtual learning systems among the students of higher institutions in Nigeria is of high importance. The perception of Higher National Diploma (HND) students of Federal Polytechnic Ede towards the use of virtual learning systems (VLS) was studied. The population of HND students of School of Business and Management Studies (SBMS) as at the time of the research was 1422 out of which 40% sample was drawn for the study making a total of 570. The types of the virtual learning systems (VLS) available at the Federal Polytechnic Ede was examined, digital competence of the students, their perception of VLS use and challenges of using VLS were also examined. Findings revealed positive perceptions towards VLS use among the understudied students, digital competencies needed for use of VLS include: basic operation skills, practical usage skills, knowledge transfer skill among others. Despite the positive perception rate of VLS use among the understudied, it was discovered that there are some hindrances to the use of virtual learning systems these include: unfavourable network connectivity, epileptic power supply, lack of smart phones among some HND students among others. The study concluded that most of the VLS are available and the students are familiar with the digital competencies needed for their use. Recommendations of possible solutions were given based on the challenges identified.

Keywords: Virtual learning systems, Internet, HND students, Perception, Use, Nigeria

Introduction

One of the technological innovations for teaching and learning activities is virtual learning systems (VLS). Arghya et al. (2020) defines virtual learning systems as computer-based (such as digital videos, tablets, projector, operating systems) learning process which links digital content, system-based administrations and mentoring support and aid in the interaction of students and teachers. The concepts virtual leaning system is used interchangeably with online learning and e-learning. Virtual learning system is a learning process that involves electronic means such as computers, mobile phones or other electronic devices and accessing the Internet. Virtual learning systems are set of useful tools that minimise students and lecturers commuting from their various homes to their institutions (Yakubu & Dasuki, 2018). In other words virtual learning systems are more of innovation into teaching and learning and offer more comfortable options for both learners and the teachers. This assertion is buttressed by Tamrat and Teferra (2020) whom averred that virtual learning systems are alternative learning methods that depend entirely on the use of Internet and other technologies without physical classroom meeting of the students and lectures.

Virtual learning system (VLS) is an electronically enabled learning system that creates end to end contacts for students and lecturers rather than physical contact mode of learning. It offers educators and learners virtually based systems geared towards creating an active and interactive learning environment. Virtual learning could be synchronous or asynchronous. According to Perveen (2016) synchronous learning type is dependent on Internet based resources and support systems through which users with connectivity can access from anywhere and learn. Synchronous system of teaching takes place at the same time between the learners and the instructors.

Asynchronous virtual learning on the other hand, involves interactive sessions where participants interact at different times. It is an on-demand service providing educational content in form of virtual classroom, webinars, online course, discussions forums and many more. In the online learning environment, the teacher-centred technique has changed to a student-centred approach (Hrastinski, 2008). Asynchronous learning at different times based on the learners' convenience in line with the course content can easily be accessed even after the delivery.

Virtual learning systems offer flexibility such that learners can learn at their own pace. In this case learners can access lectures from the comfort of homes, hostels or any other places of choice and/or at any time as long as there is Internet connectivity and electronic devices. Some of the benefits of virtual learning systems include: flexible teaching methodology, content management, a synchronous and asynchronous interaction between teachers and students, organising and structure of courses. In addition, it provides distance learning that is capable of creating new learning environments to achieve prosperous academic programme as well as provides tools for students to be in contact with peers and teachers in and outside the classroom (Rasouli et al., 2016).

Many higher institutions of learning especially in developed countries are using virtual learning systems in order to connect the students with their respective courses and programme of study (Awojide, 2020). On the other hand studies revealed that reverse is the case in many developing countries though concerted efforts are being made to follow suit. However, this has met with some challenges as a result of deficient infrastructure, mixed perception and inadequate preparedness by the institutions and students. This infers that nations of the world are at different levels of the virtual learning systems use as a result of different factors as applied to each one of them.

In most developing countries, learning is mostly done traditionally (face-to-face), thus considering virtual learning systems would require certain behavioural changes and regulatory directives in order to make it work for the learners and teachers. This has become more important because not all the students and lecturers are adequately conversant and proficient on how to participate in virtual learning platforms. As such, virtual learning can only be effective where there is adequate support system, and for such support to be sustainable, both students and facilitators must have seamless access to electronic devices, internet services as well as the required skills to navigate the platform. Such skills include but not limited to: digital competence on the part of the learners and the instructors. Furthermore, they must be attuned to the new environment and culture of learning.

Virtual learning system as an alternative mode of learning which removes the barriers created by distance between learners and educators, but was not really popular especially among Nigerian students. This is as a result of some factors associated with its use; such as digital competence, information literacy skills, self-efficacy, awareness and perception among others. However, the need for its adoption into the learning systems and use in Nigerian higher institutions have been exposed and necessitated by certain factors such as the outbreak of COVID-19 pandemic which brought virtually all human activities to a standstill globally. Nations, institution and organisations were compelled to seek for ways of returning to some of the normal activities while also taking into cognisance the safety of everyone. Incessant closure of higher institutions leading to irregular academic calendar is also another factor that necessitated use of virtual learning systems in some higher institutions in Nigeria. On this note, this research sets out to determine the perception of HND students of Federal Polytechnic Ede, towards the use of VLS. The following research questions were drawn in order to elicit information and to predict the future acceptance of use of virtual learning system based on digital competencies of the students.

Research questions

1. What are the types of virtual learning systems available in Federal Polytechnic Ede?

2. What are the required digital competencies needed by HND students of Federal Polytechnic Ede to use virtual learning systems?
3. What are the perceptions of HND students of Federal Polytechnic Ede towards the use of virtual learning systems?

Theoretical framework

The constructs of the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) was used to anchor this research. These are perceived usefulness (PU), and perceived ease of use (PEOU). These constructs were also used by Yukhymenko-Lescroart et al. (2021) in their study of A Latent Profile Analysis of University Faculty Subtypes for Mobile Technology Integration. Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) is an information systems theory introduced by Fred Davis in 1986 for his doctorate proposal and was later revised in 1989 (Davis, 1989). Technology acceptance model is an information systems theory that explains how users accept and use a technology. Yukhymenko-Lescroart et al. (2021) reported that levels of perceived usefulness of mobile technology among the faculty members, among other factors characterised their positive attitude towards the use of technology.

Akinde (2016) supported the above assertion and averred that TAM is an individual's psychological state that describes an individual's intention to use a particular technology. According to TAM, there are two factors that determine whether a technology or system will be accepted and used by its potential users. These factors are: perceived usefulness (PU), and perceived ease of use (PEOU). It is commonly believed that before using a technology/system, the potential users would put into consideration if the technology will suit the purpose for which it is intended. They will also consider their ability to use the said technology easily and without any difficulty. The researchers found out that Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) is more relevant to this study because of the two stated factors. The relevance of TAM to this study is that if the HND students of the Federal Polytechnic, Ede perceive that VLS is useful to them in their studies they will use it. In the same vein if they perceive that VLS is easy to for them to use, then they will use it. In other words the perception of HND students of Federal Polytechnic, Ede will determine whether they will use it or not. Therefore, the theory was adopted to underpin the understudied perception of VLS use.

Literature review

Virtual learning system is digitally permitted and technology-facilitated learning devices that use a digital camera, personal computers (PCs), digital videos, tablets, projector; OHP, software, operating systems which aid in the interaction of students and teachers (Eze et al., 2018). It includes other applications that support learning from a distance or face to face with the help of Personal Computer (PC). It is also known as electronic Virtual learning has moved from learning from the conventional method to contemporary driven, synergistic, customised and adaptable learning method involving learners', facilitators and instructors (Falana, 2015). The traditional method of learning was considered teacher-focused, while the learner-focus is centred on technologies which assist learners in distribution and getting contents frequently. Virtual learning covers basic and synergistic PC supported scholarship process and evaluation methods that use innovative approaches and applications to advance teaching and research (Eze et al., 2018). According to Sangra et al. (2012), the concept of virtual leaning can be portrayed as learning which utilises innovation and other educational model based on electronic media and tools. In the end, it is for enhancing the interaction and training that helps in establishing knowledge. However, later Singh and Thurman (2019) further elaborated e-learning as an experience of involving in both synchronous and asynchronous environments by incorporating multiple smart gadgets. As such, this will provide a useful pathway for students to be accessible in their learning process.

As observed by Cojocariu et al. (2014) online classes provide students with flexibility in terms of learning, regardless of place and time without any restrictions by utilising smart devices. According to Kolås (2015), an interactive tool embedded in online classes allows students to be motivated and engaging towards their learning journey. However, some disadvantages occur during the implementation. Sanjay and Narayana (2020) said there is a massive change in the educational models when it comes to implementing online classes where the adaptation process is longer. Students might face difficulties in handling it in the first place. Moreover, there are some challenges faced when it comes to adult students in using online classes.

Student's perception towards online classes in one of the research studies conducted by Koohang et al. (2016), mentioned that online learning creates active participation among students. Adding on to that, Cole et al.'s (2016) explain that some students choose online classes as the best solution than face-to-face as it creates an interest for students to participate in the online classes actively. As mentioned by Thamarana (2016) and supported by Felix (2020) that incorporating various tools such as Zoom, G-suite cloud meeting, e-classroom and Superstar provide added value in the learning process. Other virtual learning systems available for teaching and learning include e-learning resources as: WhatsApp, Google Classroom, GoogleDoc, Telegram, Youtube, TeamViewer, Moodle, Skype, Mobile classroom app., LMS (designed for distance education). In the end, it creates positive results in enhancing students' interest in learning.

Chung et al. (2020) surveyed students' readiness for online learning in Malaysia. The result shows the readiness of students to participate in online learning is slightly moderate as some of them were not ready for online learning due to lack of learners control, self-directed learning and online communication efficacy. On the challenges universities are facing towards the efforts to ensure students finish their courses on time during the corona virus pandemic, Nganga et al. (2020) noted that online learning preparedness varies from one institution to the other. Not all the student and lecturers had been trained on how to participate in online learning. Most students do not have laptops or money to buy internet bundles.

Many research studies have been conducted regarding the student's effects on communication and participation in different perspectives. Salbego and Tumolo (2015) conduct a study to investigate the student's experiences in Skype language classes. It shows that there is an increase in the development of a student's language skills. On top of that, Joksimović et al. (2015) mentioned that online classes encourage learners to communicate with peers actively. As such, that factor contributes well to the participation and involvement of each student in the online class. Nevertheless, online classes have greater control over the timing of completing the coursework, which creates a new solution for students to manage their time effectively without full guidance by lecturers (Picciano, 2017).

Methodology

The study adopts descriptive survey design to carry out the study. The study population comprised 1422 HND students in the School of Business and Management Studies (SBMS) in Federal Polytechnic, Ede, Osun State. Multi stage sampling technique was used for the study. The first stage involved purposive sampling technique which was used to cover HND students in School of Business and Management Studies (SBMS) from the eight Schools in Federal Polytechnic, Ede. The second stage was proportionate sampling technique which was used to pick 40% (570) across board the HND 1 and HND 2 students in all the departments in SBMS that have HND students. The third and the last stage used for this study was simple random sampling technique, which was used to administer the questionnaire to HND student in the five departments of the school of Business and Management where there are HND students. Questionnaire was used for data collection to elicit responses on the perception of HND students of Federal Polytechnic Ede towards the use of Virtual Learning Systems. Five hundred and seventy (570) copies of questionnaire were administered while

420 were retrieved and analysed using Statistical Product and Service Solution (SPSS) which generates frequency counts and simple percentages.

Data analysis

Table 1: Demographic information

Demographics	Frequency	%
Sex		
Male	199	47.4
Female	221	52.6
Total	420	100
Department		
Business Admin.	74	17.6
Office Technology Mgt.	83	19.8
Marketing	65	15.5
Banking and Finance	87	20.7
Accountancy	111	26.4
Total	420	100
Level		
HND I	231	55
HND II	189	45
Total	420	100

Source: Field Survey 2022

Table 1 above revealed that a total of 420 questionnaires were retrieved from the respondents. As such, going by the demographic information table, it indicates the highest sex distribution is females with 221 (52.6%) of the total population. The department with the highest respondents is accountancy with 111 respondents and the highest respondents are from HND I with 231 respondents.

Research question 1: What are the types of virtual learning systems available at FPE?

Table 2: Types of virtual learning systems available at Federal Polytechnic Ede

VLS Virtual Learning Systems	Available	Not Available
Zoom	300 (71.4%)	120 (28.6%)
Google Scholar	230 (54.8%)	190 (45.2%)
WhatsApp Group	420 (100%)	0 (0%)
Video Conferencing	320 (76.2%)	100 (23.8%)
Newsgroup	400 (95.2%)	20 (4.8%)
E-classroom	240 (57.1%)	180 (42.9%)
YAHOO MAIL Group	420 (100%)	0 (0%)
Computer Managed Learning	420 (100%)	0 (0%)
Computer Assisted Instruction	420 (100%)	0 (0%)
Interactive Online Learning	370 (88.1%)	50 (11.9%)
Individual Online Learning	400 (95.2%)	20 (4.8%)
Skype	100 (23.8%)	320 (76.2%)

Source: Field Survey 2022

The results as presented on Table 2 above revealed the available virtual learning system at Federal Polytechnic, Ede. The table shows most of the VLS systems are available, with some of them having 100% in affirmative, such as YAHOO MAIL Group, WhatsApp Group, Computer Managed Learning (CML), Computer Assisted Instruction. Individual Online Learning and e-classroom have 400 responses on availability representing 95.2% each. This shows the good rate of availability of the virtual learning systems the institution.

Research question 2: What are the required digital competencies needed in using virtual learning systems?

Table 3: Digital competencies needed for using virtual learning system (VLS)

Required digital competencies for using VLS	SA		A		D		SD	
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%
Basic digital operation skills	135	32.1	87	20.7	98	23.3	100	23.8
Practical usage skills	130	40	140	33.3	76	18.1	74	17.6
Programming knowledge	73	17.4	100	23.8	120	28.6	127	30.2
Knowledge transfer skill	70	16.7	103	24.5	124	29.5	123	29.3
Information literacy skill	150	35.7	120	28.6	73	17.4	77	18.3
Self-efficacy is required	180	42.9	90	21.4	61	14.5	89	21.2

Source: Field Survey 2022

Table 3 shows that basic digital operation skills, practical usage skills of the VLS, information literacy skills and self-efficacy are essential in using Virtual Learning Systems. Programming skills and knowledge transfer skills are at the lower rate with 73 (17.4%) and 70 (16.7%) respectively.

Research question 3: What are the perceptions of HND students in Federal Polytechnic Ede towards using virtual learning systems?

Table 4: Perception of HND students in Federal Polytechnic Ede towards using virtual learning systems

Perception towards the use of VLS	SA		A		D		SD	
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%
1. VLS complement face-to-face learning.	170	40.5	110	26.2	67	15.9	73	17.4
2. Bad Network discourages me from using VLS	195	46.4	180	42.3	40	9.5	5	1.8
3. Incessant power outage discourages me	176	41.9	84	20	110	26.2	30	7.1
4. IT technicality of VLS is too complex for me.	80	19	66	15.7	150	35.7	124	29.5
5. I do not have android phone to use for VLS	56	13.3	94	22.4	130	30.9	140	33.3
6. VLS enable me to study at pace.	176	41.9	108	25.7	110	26.2	26	6.2
7. VLS remove distance barrier.	184	43.8	120	28.6	98	23.3	18	4.3
8. High cost of data is too much for me	170	40.5	110	26.2	67	15.9	73	17.4

Source: Field Survey 2022

Result as presented in table 4 indicated the perception of the students under studied. 67 % perceived that VLS complement the traditional class room learning. 67.6% perceived that VLS

enable them to study at their own pace. 72.4% of the respondents perceived that VLS removes distance barrier as such they can study anywhere provided there is internet connectivity. 65.2% perceived that IT technicality is not a barrier to the use of VLS while 34.8% perceived that VLS is too technical for them to use in learning. The result also indicated that 40.5% perceived that the cost of data is too high as such it discourages them from using virtual learning system. Result also showed that 95% perceived that bad network is a factor that discourages the use of VLS. Some respondents perceived that the high cost of data is a challenge to the use of VLS, 66.7% of the respondents are in support of this. Also, incessant power supply was perceived as a challenge to the use of VLS with 35.7% response. The table also shows most users have smart phones to facilitate the use of VLS as indicated that only 56 respondents which cover 13.3% of the respondents do not have smart phones for VLS use.

Discussion of findings

The research has exposed the various types of VLS available as well as the perception of HND students of Federal Polytechnic Ede towards the use of VLS. Findings indicated that the students are favourably disposed to the systems due to their convenience and for complementing the face to face teaching and learning method. This is in support of Felix (2020) who stated that the use of various VLS provide added value to the learning process. In other words HND students of Federal Polytechnic Ede perceived the use of VLS to be an added value to learning. Some of the VLS use include: WhatsApp group, Yahoo mail group discussion among others. The required digital competencies needed are mostly, basic operation skills, practical usage skills and information literacy skills. Self-efficacy is also requirement. The findings revealed that most of the students perceived that VLS is useful to them and that they have what it take to it, as such it will be easy for them to use. This is in support of Yuhymenko-Lescroart et al. (2021) who reported that perceived usefulness of mobile technology determines their positive attitude towards the use of technology. They perceived it allows them to beat distance barrier and to study at their pace among other benefits. Nevertheless, associated problems with the use of VLS include high cost of data, bad network, to mention a few.

Conclusion

The study examined the perception of HND students of Federal Polytechnic Ede towards the use of VLS. The study concluded that there are different types of VLS available in Federal Polytechnic, Ede and the understudied perceived VLS as better learning options due to the convenience over face to face or physical classroom learning. It was discovered that the students under study have the digital competencies needed in using VLS because they perceived VLS are not complex to use many students are conversant with them. However, the study has revealed some major challenges to the use of the systems among some of the students which include cost of smart phones, cost of data, network failure and incessant power supply as factors constituting challenges.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusion of this research, the following recommendations were drawn:

1. More users friendly Virtual Learning Systems needed: Although, there are several virtual learning systems in place these days, but the user friendliness warrants one preference over the other. As such, there is the need for a more user friendly online learning systems from the technology industries.
2. Eradication of power failures: The government should look into the issue of power supply in the country at large and the school management should provide alternative power supply as back up.

3. There is need for increase in network bandwidth. In other to have a stronger network connectivity the bandwidth should be increase by the telecom operators are to also strengthen the band with for more network stability.
4. The economy of the country should be addressed to deal with the inflation so as to bring down the prices of smart phones to allow many students to afford the for VLS use.

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